

ANXIETY AND STRESS ARE THE PART OF EVERY DAY LIFE

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ABSTRACT:

Anxiety is a feeling of nervousness, apprehension, fear, or worry. Some fears and worries are justified, such as worry about a loved one or in anticipation of taking a quiz, test, or other examination. Problem anxiety interferes with the sufferer's ability to sleep or otherwise function. It is noteworthy that teenagers are particularly susceptible to having irritability as a symptom of a number of emotional problems, including anxiety. Anxiety may occur without a cause, or it may occur based on a real situation but may be out of proportion to what would normally be expected. Severe anxiety can have a serious impact on daily life.

Anxiety disorders may be caused by environmental factors, medical factors, genetics, brain chemistry, substance abuse, or a combination of these. It is most commonly triggered by the stress in our lives. Usually anxiety is a response to outside forces, but it is possible that we make ourselves anxious with "negative self-talk" - a habit of always telling ourselves the worst will happen.

Anxiety is a feeling of fear, unease, and worry. The source of these symptoms is not always known. Alternative Names:

Anxiety; Feeling uptight; Stress; Tension; Jitters; Apprehension

Stress is a normal feeling. In small doses, stress can help you get things done. Stress does not affect everyone the same way.

Many people feel stress symptoms in their body. You may be having pain in your abdomen, headaches, and muscle tightness or pain.

Medically, it has been established that chronic symptoms of anxiety and stress can crumble our body's immune system. Irrespective of the nature of the causes of stress—real or perceived—our subconscious mind reacts with the same body response by releasing stress hormones equal to the degree of our fear, worry or sense of threat. It brings about changes in the body's biochemical state with extra epinephrine and other adrenal steroids such as hydrocortisone in the bloodstream. It also induces increased palpitation and blood pressure in the body with mental manifestations such as anger, fear, worry or aggression. In short, stress creates anomalies in our body's homeostasis. When the extra chemicals in our bloodstream don't get used up or the stress situation persists, it makes our body prone to mental and physical illnesses.

INTRODUCTION:

Humans is taxonomically known as *Homo sapiens*, Latin for "wise man" or "knowing man" are the only living species in the *Homo* genus. Anatomically modern humans originated in Africa about 200,000 years ago, reaching full behavioural modernity around 50,000 years ago.

The English adjective *human* is a Middle English loanword from Old French *human*, ultimately from Latin *humanus* the adjective form of *homo* "man". The word's use as a noun (with a plural: *humans*) dates to the 16th century. The native English term *man* can refer to the species generally and could formerly refer to specific individuals of either sex. The species binomial *Homo sapiens* was coined by *Carl Linnaeus* in his 18th century work *Systema Naturae*, and he himself is the lectotype specimen.

Humans have a highly developed brain and are capable of abstract reasoning, language, introspection and problem solving. Humans are uniquely adept at utilizing systems of communication for self-expression, the exchange of ideas, and organization. Humans create complex social structures composed of many cooperating and competing groups, from families and kinship networks, to nations. Social interactions between humans have established an extremely wide variety of values, social norms, and rituals, which together form the basis of human society.

DEFINITION OF HUMAN:

1. Human is any individual of the genus *Homo*, especially a member of the species *Homo sapiens*.

2. Human is a person, especially as distinguished from other animals or as representing the human species: living conditions not fit for human beings; a very generous being.

PSYCHOLOGY OF HUMANS

The human brain, the focal point of the central nervous system in humans, controls the peripheral nervous system. Generally regarded as more capable of these higher order activities, the human brain is believed to be more "intelligent" in general than that of any other known species. Modern anthropology has tended to bear out Darwin's proposition that "the difference in mind between man and the higher animals, great as it is, certainly is one of degree and not of kind".

Humans are variously said to possess consciousness, self-awareness, and a mind, which correspond roughly to the mental processes of thought.

The philosopher of cognitive science Daniel Dennett, for example, argues that there is no such thing as a narrative centre called the "mind", but that instead there is simply a collection of sensory inputs and outputs: different kinds of "software" running in parallel. Psychologist B.F. Skinner argued that the mind is an explanatory fiction that diverts attention from environmental causes of behaviour, and that what are commonly seen as mental processes may be better conceived of as forms of covert verbal behaviour.

ANXIETY

Anxiety is a feeling of nervousness, apprehension, fear, or worry. Some fears and worries are justified, such as worry about a loved one or in anticipation of taking a quiz, test, or other examination. Problem anxiety interferes with the sufferer's ability to sleep or otherwise function. It is noteworthy that teenagers are particularly susceptible to having irritability as a symptom of a number of emotional problems, including anxiety. Anxiety may occur without a cause, or it may occur based on a real situation but may be out of proportion to what would normally be expected. Severe anxiety can have a serious impact on daily life.

- Anxiety can be accompanied by a variety of physical symptoms. Most commonly, these symptoms are related to the heart, lungs, nervous, and gastrointestinal systems. You may have upset stomach, diarrhea, trouble breathing, feel as if you may faint or are having a heart attack.

What is generalized anxiety disorder (GAD)?

Generalized anxiety disorder (GAD) is a mood disorder that is characterized by multiple and/or nonspecific worries. The fear associated with GAD interferes with the person's ability to sleep, think, or function in some other way. Symptoms of anxiety are even described in the word itself. Specifically, the word *anxiety* comes from the Latin word *anxietas*, which means to choke or upset. The symptoms therefore include emotional or behavioural symptoms as well as ways of thinking that are responses to feeling as if one is in danger.

Generalized anxiety disorder facts

- Generalized anxiety disorder (GAD) is a mood disorder that is characterized by multiple and/or nonspecific worries that interfere with the person's life in some way.
- The most common anxiety disorders are specific phobias. Other anxiety disorders include social anxiety disorder, panic disorder, generalized anxiety disorder, obsessive compulsive disorder, and posttraumatic stress disorder.
- GAD is quite common, affecting millions of people.
- While there is no single cause of GAD, there are many factors that increase the risk of developing this disorder.
- Signs and symptoms of anxiety can include those that are emotional or behavioural and ways of thinking that are responses to feeling as if one is in danger.
- The similarities and differences in symptoms of anxiety in adults compared to children and adolescents depend on the diagnosis.
- There seem to be gender differences in the expression of anxiety.
- If a medical or mental health professional suspects that you have GAD, you will likely undergo an extensive medical interview and physical examination.
- Treatment of GAD usually involves some combination of lifestyle changes, psychotherapy, and/or medication.

- As anything that is ingested carries risk of side effects, it is important for the anxiety disorder sufferer to work closely with the prescribing doctor to decide whether treatment with medications is an appropriate intervention, and if so, which medication should be administered.
- There are many possible complications associated with anxiety.
- Various lifestyle choices and family interventions can help prevent anxiety.
- GAD usually requires treatment for it to resolve.
- There are many support groups for people who suffer from generalized anxiety disorder.

Anxiety disorders may be caused by environmental factors, medical factors, genetics, brain chemistry, substance abuse, or a combination of these. It is most commonly triggered by the stress in our lives. Usually anxiety is a response to outside forces, but it is possible that we make ourselves anxious with "negative self-talk" - a habit of always telling ourselves the worst will happen.

Environmental and external factors

Environmental factors that are known to cause several types of anxiety include:

- Trauma from events such as abuse, victimization, or the death of a loved one
- Stress in a personal relationship, marriage, friendship, and divorce
- Stress at work
- Stress from school
- Stress about finances and money
- Stress from a natural disaster
- Lack of oxygen in high altitude areas

Medical factors

Anxiety is associated with medical factors such as anemia, asthma, infections, and several heart conditions. Some medically-related causes of anxiety include:

- Stress from a serious medical illness

- Side effects of medication
- Symptoms of a medical illness
- Lack of oxygen from emphysema, or pulmonary embolism (a blood clot in the lung)

Substance use and abuse

It is estimated that about half of patients who utilize mental health services for anxiety disorders such as GAD, panic disorder, or social phobia are doing so because of alcohol or benzodiazepine dependence. More generally, anxiety is also known to result from:

- Intoxication from an illicit drug, such as cocaine or amphetamines
- Withdrawal from an illicit drug, such as heroin, or from prescription drugs like Vicodin, benzodiazepines, or barbiturates

Genetics

It has been suggested by some researchers that a family history of anxiety increases the likelihood that a person will develop it. That is, some people may have a genetic predisposition that gives them a greater chance of suffering from anxiety disorders.

EFFECTS OF STRESS:

Medically, it has been established that chronic symptoms of anxiety and stress can crumble our body's immune system. Irrespective of the nature of the causes of stress—real or perceived—our subconscious mind reacts with the same body response by releasing stress hormones equal to the degree of our fear, worry or sense of threat. It brings about changes in the body's biochemical state with extra epinephrine and other adrenal steroids such as hydrocortisone in the bloodstream. It also induces increased palpitation and blood pressure in the body with mental manifestations such as anger, fear, worry or aggression. In short, stress creates anomalies in our body's homeostasis. When the extra chemicals in our bloodstream don't get used up or the stress situation persists, it makes our body prone to mental and physical illnesses. For example, imagine a secretary in an office. Her boss comes in, angry and furious. He starts blasting the secretary for no apparent reasons. Now, her activated adrenaline cycle would tell her to flee or fight. Her senses become acute, muscles tighten heartbeats and blood pressure increase and brain activity speeds up. She would probably like to walk out or alternatively,

turn around and punch him in the face. But she does neither, for to do so might mean losing her job. So what follows? She burns up a lot of her body energy without achieving anything. At the end of the day she would be left mentally, physically and emotionally exhausted—classic symptoms of anxiety and stress. It can happen to anybody from a high profile businessman to a student, an executive or a homemaker. All are burning out their energies to defend themselves from their real or perceived causes of stress. Stress & Aging Aging is a natural and gradual process, except under extreme circumstances such as stress or grief. The constant stressors or stress conditions result in a loss in neural and hormonal balance. This loss of balance will cause increased oxidative damage accelerating aging in our body. That`s because, chronic disturbances in body homeostasis ultimately affect our hormone secreting glands, cell repair and collagen in our skin and connecting tissues. Immune and neural degenerative diseases prevent this otherwise inevitable process from following the normal and healthy course of events.

STRESS AND ANXIETY

Stress can come from any event or thought that makes you feel frustrated, angry, or nervous.

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Many people feel stress symptoms in their body. You may be having pain in your abdomen, headaches, and muscle tightness or pain.

When you are much stressed, you may notice:

- A faster heart rate
- Skipped heartbeats
- Rapid breathing
- Sweating
- Trembling
- Dizziness

Other symptoms include:

- Loose stools
- Frequent need to pee
- Dry mouth
- Problems swallowing

You may have a harder time focusing, feel tired most of the time, or lose your temper more often. Stress may also cause sexual problems. It can also cause problems with falling or staying asleep and nightmares.

CAUSES

Many people have stress when they need to adapt or change.

Examples are:

- Starting a new job or school
- Moving to a new home
- Getting married
- Having a child
- Breaking up with someone

An injury or illness to you, a friend, or a loved one is a common cause of stress. Feelings of stress and anxiety are common in people who feel depressed and sad.

Some drugs may cause or worsen symptoms of stress.

These can include:

- Some inhaler medicines used to treat asthma
- Thyroid drugs
- Some diet pills
- Some cold remedies

Caffeine, cocaine, alcohol, and tobacco products may also cause or make symptoms of stress or anxiety worse.

When these feelings happen often, a person may have an anxiety disorder. Other problems where stress may be present are:

- Obsessive-compulsive disorder
- Panic disorder
- Post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD)

Home Care

- What relieves stress is not the same for everyone. Making certain lifestyle changes is the best start.
- Start with eating a well-balanced, healthy diet as well as getting enough sleep and exercise, also, limit caffeine and alcohol intake and don't use nicotine, cocaine, or other street drugs.
- Finding healthy, fun ways to cope with stress helps most people. You can learn and practice ways to help you relax. Find out about yoga, tai chi, or meditation.
- Take breaks from work. Make sure to balance fun activities with your job and family duties. Schedule some leisure time every day. Spend time with people you enjoy, including your family.
- Try learning to make things with your hands, playing an instrument, or listening to music.
- Think about what might be giving you stress. Keep a diary of what is going on when you have these feelings.
- Then, find someone you trust who will listen to you. Often just talking to a friend or loved one is all that you need to feel better. Most areas also have support groups and hotlines that can help.
- Ask your health care provider if any drugs or medicines you are taking can cause anxiety.

STRESS MANAGEMENT

Stress management is the need of the hour. However hard we try to go beyond a stress situation, life seems to find new ways of stressing us out and plaguing us with anxiety attacks. Moreover, be it our anxiety, mind-body exhaustion or our erring attitudes, we tend to overlook causes of stress and the conditions triggered by those. In such unsettling moments we often forget that stressors, if not escapable, are fairly manageable and treatable.

Stress, either quick or constant, can induce risky body-mind disorders. Immediate disorders such as dizzy spells, anxiety attacks, tension, sleeplessness, nervousness and muscle cramps can all result in chronic health problems. They may also affect our immune, cardiovascular and nervous systems and lead individuals to habitual addictions, which are inter-linked with stress.

Like "stress reactions", "relaxation responses" and stress management techniques are some of the body's important built-in response systems. As a relaxation response the body tries to get back balance in its homeostasis. Some hormones released during the 'fight or flight' situation prompt the body to replace the lost carbohydrates and fats, and restore the energy level. The knotted nerves, tightened muscles and an exhausted mind crave for looseness. Unfortunately, today, we don't get relaxing and soothing situations without asking. To be relaxed we have to strive to create such situations. Recognizing A Stressor. We cope better with stressful situation, when we encounter them voluntarily. In cases of relocation, promotion or layoff, adventurous sports or having a baby, we tend to respond positively under stress. But, when we are compelled into such situations against our will or knowledge, more often than not, we wilt at the face of unknown and imagined threats. For instance, stress may mount when one is coerced into undertaking some work against one's will. Laughter.

Adopting a humorous view towards life's situations can take the edge off everyday stressors. Not being too serious or in a constant alert mode helps maintain the equanimity of mind and promote clear thinking. Being able to laugh stress away is the smartest way to ward off its effects.

A sense of humor also allows us to perceive and appreciate the incongruities of life and provides moments of delight. The emotions we experience directly affect our immune system. The positive emotions can create neurochemical changes that buffer the immunosuppressive effects of stress.

During stress, the adrenal gland releases corticosteroids, which are converted to cortisol in the blood stream. These have an immunosuppressive effect. Dr. Lee Berk and fellow researcher Dr. Stanley Tan at Loma Linda University School of Medicine have produced carefully controlled studies showing that the experience of laughter lowers serum cortisol levels, increases the amount and activity of T lymphocytes—the natural killer cells. Laughter also increases the number of T cells that have suppresser receptors.

Laughter and its effects against Stress:

- Laughter lowers blood pressure and reduces hypertension.

- It provides good cardiac conditioning especially for those who are unable to perform physical exercise.
- Laughter cleanses the lungs and body tissues of accumulated stale air as it empties more air than it takes in. It is beneficial for patients suffering from emphysema and other respiratory ailments.
- It increases muscle flexion, relaxation and fluent blood circulation in body.
- Boosts immune function by raising levels of infection-fighting T-cells, disease-fighting proteins called Gamma-interferon and disease-destroying antibodies called B-cells.
- Laughter triggers the release of endorphins—body's natural painkillers.
- Produces a general sense of well-being.

HOW TO HEAL ANXIETY

Anxiety is a condition, just like any other, that can wreak havoc on your life and leave you stressed, lonely, unemployed, and just generally all-around miserable. This is where I found myself when I was struggling with social anxiety disorder (SAD) and generalized anxiety disorder (GAD). However, again much like any other condition, it is something that can be treated successfully, and you can reach the opposite extreme where you have tons of wonderful friends, fulfilling employment, romantic success, and a general feeling of happiness and well-being.

So, how do you heal anxiety? Unfortunately, for many the solution is to visit the doctor and see which type of medication he prescribes. This is one possible step that you can take, but like any other condition, using a more comprehensive approach enhances the level of success you experience. If clichés make more sense to you, “you get out of it what you put into it.” Besides taking a few steps, there is an additional point to keep in mind: what works for one person may not work for another; it is up to you to build your own plan based on what experience teaches you.

How to Cure Anxiety:

Here are some of the techniques I have learned that can help to cure anxiety:

1. Accept help from a professional counselor or psychologist

This is very scary for people in Western society where we are taught to live independently, but life works differently. Using the aid of knowledgeable others can be incredibly helpful. Counselors typically have very gentle personalities and an open, calm, and accepting manner. Their goal is to make it as comfortable as possible for you to interact with them. Attempting to recover from anxiety on your own does work, but working with a counselor is like strapping on a jetpack – it helps you to grow at an incredibly rapid pace. One caveat is that not all counselors or psychologists can work with all people. If things simply are not working between you and your counselor, feel free to move on to another one.

2. Exercise regularly

Not only is exercise good for you physically, but it is also great for reducing anxiety and stress. Exercise releases endorphins which cause you to experience a general sense of happiness and well-being. All you need to do to gain the benefits is 3 sessions per week of 20 minutes of moderate-intensity exercise.

3. Regular journaling

For me, I have found it incredibly helpful to journal in order to collect my thoughts at the end of the day. I typically spend 15-20 minutes writing about what happened. It helps me to gain clarity and focus, and there is something about putting words on paper that helps to remove the anxious thoughts from my head. While helpful for me, I have heard of many people who completely hate writing. If this is the case for you, this is one of those things that seems to be optional. But, it is always good to at least have the awareness of another tool to reduce your anxiety.

4. Avoid foods that cause anxiety

There are a few different foods and substances that will increase your anxiety if consumed. Caffeine and alcohol, which are difficult to avoid in American society, are two of the chief aggravators of anxiety. If you are like me and you really enjoy drinks which contain these two substances, the good news is you do not have to completely eliminate them from

your diet. Instead, you just have to minimize your intake. "Minimizing," in this case, means like 2-3 caffeinated and alcoholic drinks in a week. Of course, if you are willing to live with more anxiety, you can consume more, but this is the general guideline.

5. Eat foods that help to reduce anxiety

Be sure to stay well-hydrated. Dehydration can cause fatigue, and one of the body's responses to fatigue can be anxiety. Foods rich in complex carbohydrates such as *pastas, brown rice, sweet potatoes, corn, peas, and beans* are excellent for maintaining your energy levels and keeping anxiety down. Another anxiety-reducing substance is tryptophan, and foods high in tryptophan include milk, oats, nuts, and peanut butter. Finally, one vitamin to make sure you have in your diet is vitamin B-6. This vitamin helps to regulate serotonin, a neurotransmitter which is responsible for managing your anxiety levels.

6. Maintain a supportive social network

A supportive social network is one that makes you feel okay with having your struggle with anxiety. Additionally, people who are supportive will offer to help you through the difficulty, or perhaps to find a new way to understand situations that are causing you anxiety. If people are trying to make you feel guilty, embarrassed, or simply do not want to acknowledge your anxiety condition, the best thing to do is to distance yourself from them. Of course, if they begin to show an understanding of anxiety, feel free to bring them back into your lives. You do not have to remove them from your life completely, but you will find that conversations about anxiety will end up going nowhere. This may be the second most difficult part of getting better from anxiety.

7. Continue to take risks

Without a doubt, this is the most difficult step in recovering from anxiety. For a while, it may be necessary to retreat from the outside world, find some help, think things over, and figure out how you are going to approach life now that you have recognized anxiety's effects. But, eventually, there will come a time where talking and thinking must translate to action. Action means that you are actively putting yourself in situations that make you anxious. Most people are surprised when they do this because they actually experience *more* anxiety! But, never fear, because that is completely normal. You are moving outside of your usual comfort zone, and anxiety is a natural response for all people; the difficulty for people with anxiety disorders is that they experience too much anxiety in

comparison to the average person. As you continue to take risks and work through the difficult situations, you will find that eventually you begin to grow in self-confidence, and people or situations that used to cause you anxiety now cause you little or no anxiety.

8. Use medication

For many, this is the first step to recovering from anxiety. However, medication is a short-term *false* fix to a long-term *real* problem. When you take medication, it simply reduces the intensity of the physiological effects of anxiety (shaking, sweating, tingling etc...) and the accompanying emotions. If you have social anxiety, you do not suddenly become a confident and competent extrovert; you still have to take risks and do the work. Additionally, it can take much time and thousands of dollars before you find a medication and dosage that is right for you. A certain medication may work for *most* people, but not *all* people. And finally, the side effects of medication may end up outweighing the benefits. All that being said, medication does have its place, but it has its highest level of effectiveness when working in combination with the other factors given before.

CONCLUSION:

Overall, the most important point to draw out is that anxiety is a challenge that requires a comprehensive, rather than singular approach. The more of these cures you use, the lower your anxiety level will be. If you feel confused or frightened, hopefully you must think that in which direction to go in the future. Good luck to everyone who chooses to help themselves and heal their anxiety.

REFERENCES:

- Bhati, Amritpal Kaur et all (2012) *Stress Management strategies for mental fitness*, Paper presented in National Seminar on Manage your Mind: Guidelines for Mental Fitness of Teachers and Students, sponsored by Director General of Higher Education, Haryana, org. by DR.G.D. D. A. V. College of Education for women, Karnal (Haryana).

- Bhati, Amritpal Kaur et all (2012) *The Secret to Lead a balanced and Happy life (Stress free)* Golden Research Thought, vol. I, Issue-X, April 2012, pp. 42-45. ISSN-2230-7850.
- Gupta, M. K. (2011) *How to control Mind and to be Stress-Free*, Pustak Mahal, New Delhi, pp.55-76
- <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Human>
- <http://dictionary.reference.com/browse/human+being>
- http://www.emedicinehealth.com/anxiety/article_em.htm
- <http://www.medicinenet.com/anxiety/article.htm>
- <http://www.thechangeblog.com/how-to-heal-anxiety/>
- <http://www.lifepositive.com/mind/psychology/stress/stress-management.asp>
- <http://www.lifepositive.com/mind/psychology/stress/symptoms-of-anxiety.asp>
- <http://www.medicalnewstoday.com/info/anxiety/what-causes-anxiety.php>
- <http://www.lifepositive.com/mind/psychology/stress/symptoms-of-anxiety.asp>
- <http://health.nytimes.com/health/guides/symptoms/stress-and-anxiety/overview.html>

